

Bridging Smart Divide for Rural America: Visions from Southern Illinois

A WHITE PAPER

AUTHORS:

Sabah Tajin Tarique, Graduate Research Assistant, Geography and Environmental Resources, Southern Illinois University Carbondale

Ruopu Li, Professor, Geography and Environmental Resources, Southern Illinois University Carbondale

ADVISORY COMMITTEE:

Angie Bailey, Director, Community Health, Community Benefits Department, Southern Illinois Healthcare

Tiffany R. George, Executive Director, Southern Five County Regional Planning Commission

Katharine Juul, Director, SIU Center for Rural Health and Social Service Development

John Jackson, Professor Emeritus, Paul Simon Public Policy Institute, Southern Illinois University Carbondale

John Lenzini, Community Development Manager, City of Carbondale

Cary Minnis, Executive Director, Greater Egypt Regional Planning and Development Commission

Dawn Roberts, Ph.D. (c), Population Health, Southern Illinois University Carbondale; Council member, City of Carbondale

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The rapid growth of smart technologies has reshaped how communities deliver essential services, from healthcare to education. Yet, rural regions across the United States are being left behind in this transformation. This white paper introduces the concept of the smart divide, a new form of digital inequalities that emerge not only from limited access to broadband and digital devices but also from deeper gaps in infrastructure readiness, digital skills, and social support systems, and potential solutions to address the divide and advance the resilience of rural digital economies.

Unlike the traditional digital divide, which centers on basic internet access, the smart divide reflects the growing inability of some communities to participate meaningfully in next-generation systems powered by big data, artificial intelligence, and smart applications. These disparities are especially pronounced in rural areas, where aging infrastructure, low population density, and persistent poverty create major barriers to adoption and long-term sustainability.

This white paper focuses on two communities in Southern Illinois—Cairo (Alexander County) and Carbondale (Jackson County)—to examine how the smart divide is already unfolding. Although different in size and classification, both communities face similar challenges: economic hardship, racial and ethnic diversity, and limited capacity to support digital health and education systems. The COVID-19 pandemic brought these issues into sharper focus, as essential services moved online and many rural residents were left without the tools or support needed to keep up.

Drawing on these case studies, we argue that addressing the smart divide requires a broader approach than simply expanding broadband. It calls for targeted investment in both technological infrastructure and social infrastructure, including workforce development, education, and public institutions that help bridge the gap between people and technology.

As the nation moves toward smarter and connected systems, ensuring rural communities are not left behind is not just a matter of equity, but of national resilience. This white paper offers a framework for understanding the smart divide in rural America and outlines strategies to bridge this divide, starting with rural Southern Illinois.

INTRODUCTION

The rise of Smart Applications and Services (SASs; e.g., smart education and health) driven by the advancements in Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) has fundamentally transformed modern society, shaping how we work, communicate, access healthcare, and receive education. These technologies and services reinforce each other: new ICT infrastructure enables more SAS adoption, while the demand for SASs accelerates the expansion of ICT infrastructure (Li, Chen, and Wu 2020). This dynamic has given rise to the vision of Smart Communities (SCs), which are technology-integrated, data-driven, and efficiency-minded social systems.

However, this vision is largely grounded in the experience of urban centers. The conventional blueprint for SCs assumes high-density broadband coverage, stable infrastructure, and populations well-prepared to engage with smart tools. These assumptions do not hold in decentralized rural regions, where ICT development is patchy, populations are aging, and communities face longstanding geographic, economic, and social disadvantages (Malecki 2003; Esteban-Navarro et al. 2020; Philip and Williams 2019). As a result, rural America remains largely excluded from the smart transformation.

The inequality in ICT access—often called the digital divide—has traditionally been framed as a problem of broadband availability. But recent studies emphasize that this divide is both technological and social (Schaffers et al. 2011; Kitchin 2014; Kitchin et al. 2019). While infrastructure gaps are important, so too are disparities in digital skills, education levels, and cultural attitudes toward technology. These layered inequalities

are giving rise to the "Smart Divide" a deeper and more systemic separation in the ability of communities to meaningfully participate in and benefit from smart innovations.

To understand and address this evolving challenge, a planning team led by Southern Illinois University has partnered with local partners, including the Greater Egypt Regional Planning and Development Commission, the Southern Five Regional Planning District and Development Commission, City of Carbondale, and Southern Illinois Healthcare. Together, they are working to explore the unique obstacles and potential opportunities facing Southern Illinois as it confronts the Smart Divide—and to envision a more inclusive future for rural America.

WHAT IS SMART DIVIDE

The *smart divide* refers to a new and evolving form of social inequality emerging in the era of Smart Communities. According to Li, Chen and Wu (2020), the smart divide is an inequality stemming from the uneven penetration and maturity of smart ICT infrastructure, such as broadband networks, and Smart Applications and Services (SASs), like smart healthcare or e-government tools. This inequality is further reinforced by differences in digital skills, education levels, and available resources across individuals and communities.

The smart divide encompasses two key dimensions.

- The **technological dimension** that relates to the uneven availability and capability of smart infrastructure and services. Many rural areas rely on outdated communication networks that cannot support data-intensive systems. As smart applications increasingly depend on high-speed broadband and advanced computing tools, these gaps limit deployment, reduce service quality, and delay innovation in the underserved rural regions.
- The **social dimension** that reflects disparities in human capital and social support systems. Communities vary widely in terms of digital literacy, technical expertise, and institutional support. Low levels of education, limited access to training, and a shortage of skilled labor all make it more difficult for residents to adopt and benefit from smart technologies.

Unlike traditional technology gaps, the smart divide is not just about access to the internet or smart devices. It involves more complex and layered issues, including outdated infrastructure that cannot support data-intensive systems, insufficient data capability in rural areas, high costs for deploying and maintaining smart systems, and a shortage of skilled technical labor. Smart infrastructures today demand significantly higher levels of data capability. Technologies such as big data, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things require robust computing, networking, and software systems to function effectively. However, many rural regions still rely on communication systems developed decades ago, which are unable to support these newer technologies. As a

result, smart services either remain unavailable or are delivered with reduced quality, affordability, or reliability in rural areas. Moreover, small and dispersed rural markets often discourage service providers from investing in smart infrastructures and SASs, leaving these areas with limited access to innovations that are becoming standard in urban regions.

A NOTE ON DIGITAL DIVIDE VS SMART DIVIDE

While related, the smart divide and the digital divide are conceptually distinct. The digital divide refers primarily to disparities in access to basic ICTs such as internet connectivity and digital devices. The smart divide, in contrast, arises from more advanced demands related to smart technologies and services. It reflects the inability of older infrastructure and limited local capacity to support next-generation systems. Simply expanding internet access and devices are not enough. Without deliberate planning, investment, and coordination, the smart divide risks becoming a deeper and more persistent form of exclusion in the smart era.

METHODOLOGY

This project, financially supported by the National Science Foundation (NSF), examines how rural communities can avoid falling further behind in the forthcoming smart transition. Using Cairo and Carbondale in Southern Illinois as case studies, we explored how to build smarter, more inclusive systems for health and education, two areas that exhibited urgent community demands during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The pandemic pushed services like doctor visits and classrooms online almost overnight. For many rural residents, this sudden shift exposed how unprepared their communities were. Limited broadband, lack of digital tools, and low digital literacy made them difficult to keep up. These challenges suggest a deeper, ongoing issue: rural communities are often left behind as technology advances. In other words, **the smart divide was not a hypothetical and distant threat but one that had been unfolding in full swing.**

We focus on two communities: Cairo and Carbondale. While very different in size, both face long-term struggles. Cairo is a small rural town with just over 1,700 residents. Carbondale is larger with about 22,000 people, and is classified as urban in rural Southern Illinois. Both towns are located in counties that have faced persistent poverty for more than 40 years. These communities are also diverse in race and ethnicity. Nearly 70 percent of the population is Black, and the poverty rate is over 40 percent in Cairo. At the same time, both towns lack the infrastructure, digital tools, and workforce needed to fully adopt and use smart health and smart education services. Therefore, various social and infrastructural vulnerabilities make Cairo and Carbondale valuable examples for understanding how different populations experience barriers related to technology and service delivery.

The findings presented below are drawn from a mixed-methods approach comprising in-depth interviews and mail surveys conducted between Fall 2021 and Spring 2023.

A total of 50 interviews were conducted. Twenty interviews focused on the challenges of online education, engaging a diverse group of participants including teachers, parents, senior citizens, broadband developers, non-profit representatives, and government officials. The telehealth component involved 30 interviews with participants from Cairo (13) and Carbondale (17), including both patients who used telehealth services and those who did not, as well as healthcare providers.

To complement the qualitative data, a mail survey was conducted with 262 residents from Cairo and Carbondale. Among the respondents, 57% were from Carbondale and 43% from Cairo. The majority identified as women (67%), with men representing 32%, and 1% identifying as nonbinary or other. Racial and ethnic composition was

predominantly White (51%) and Black (42%), with smaller percentages identifying as Asian, Latino, or other ethnicities. Educational attainment varied, with most respondents holding at least some college education; 27% had a bachelor's degree, 15% held a master's degree, and 7% possessed a Ph.D. or professional degree.

Survey results revealed that Carbondale residents were significantly more likely to have greater digital access and resources, including a higher number of working household computers, household internet access, cellular data plans, wired broadband connections, and faster internet speeds. Specifically, the average download and upload speeds reported for Cairo were 13.17 Mbps and 8.17 Mbps respectively, while Carbondale residents reported substantially higher speeds of 138.03 Mbps (download) and 30.00 Mbps (upload). By focusing on Cairo and Carbondale, this project looks closely at how the smart divide plays out on the ground. The goal is not just to point out the gaps but to find opportunities to close them, and to better support rural communities in **building resilient future-ready rural communities**.

NEED FOR SPEED- ROLE OF WIRELESS NETWORK

Access to a fast, reliable internet is no longer a luxury, it's the foundation for modern healthcare, education, business, and daily life. Yet in many rural areas, traditional broadband infrastructure simply hasn't kept up. Fixed broadband networks, like cable or fiber, are expensive to build and maintain in low-density regions. As a result, many small towns are left behind in the shift toward digital life. One potential solution in this case is wireless networks. Compared to fixed infrastructure, it's faster to deploy, more flexible, and often more affordable, especially for households that don't need or can't afford premium service. Technologies like 4G LTE, 5G, and emerging satellite options (like Starlink) offer hope for rural communities that have waited too long for wired solutions. In fact, 4G LTE coverage reached more than 90% of rural areas in the U.S. by 2019, compared to just 82.7% for fixed broadband.

We wanted to understand what internet speeds rural residents actually experience in their daily lives, so we conducted on-the-ground speed tests in Carbondale and Cairo. The results were clear: wireless networks are more widely available than fixed network, but their performance is often too slow or unstable to support critical uses like telehealth and online education. Telehealth and smart education require at least 10 Mbps download and 5 Mbps upload speeds for effective use—speeds often unmet in rural regions. In Cairo, nearly every census block had limited provider options and speeds that consistently fell short of what's needed. In Carbondale, there were more choices and better speeds in some areas, but even there, the quality of service varied depending on location. While Carbondale showed some service variability across neighborhoods, Cairo's speeds were consistently low across all census blocks. Despite strong signal strength in some areas, actual performance remained insufficient to support high-quality smart services.

HOW SMART DIVIDE SHAPED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCES IN SOUTHERN ILLINOIS

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed deep educational inequities in Southern Illinois communities, where the smart divide—rooted in disparities in broadband access, infrastructure, and social support—shaped vastly different online learning experiences. While Carbondale schools were able to implement structured, synchronous instruction during school closures, Cairo students largely experienced a fragmented and asynchronous learning process. In Cairo, parents picked up paper packets from some schools with little to no digital instruction, while Carbondale schools conducted live virtual classes and offered one-on-one support to struggling students.

From the start of through the end of the 2020-21 school year, the Cairo school district was asynchronous with very little instruction. Teachers in Cairo could not hold synchronous classes due to internet issues and they mainly relied on the internet mainly for homework submissions. Parents picked up packages of homework at the school front desk and students submitted answers online. Many households lacked basic access, and even those provided with hotspots often experienced connection issues. A Cairo school board member described the situation during the pandemic as “really a big mess.” A 65-year-old educator had to walk to school outside of work hours just to use the internet.

“The whole school system here got terrible during the pandemic and online school. They just cannot work from home, that’s all”.

Cairo residents frequently expressed frustration with unreliable internet services, unaffordable rates, and a lack of provider options. Some residents paid upwards of \$85 per month for service that frequently failed or was entirely inaccessible—yet they were still billed.

In contrast, Carbondale offered a more structured and flexible approach to remote learning. After initial school closures, the district quickly adopted synchronous online instruction and a hybrid model that adapted to public health conditions. Students and educators had access to multiple internet providers, high-speed service, and district-supported hotspot programs. Carbondale households reported fewer technical difficulties, more device availability (on average five computer-like devices per home compared to only two in Cairo), and better service reliability. Importantly, Carbondale residents paid an average of \$71 per month—less than Cairo—for significantly faster and more dependable internet.

Access to the public internet also differed significantly. While Carbondale residents had multiple reliable options including libraries and community centers offering broadband and device support, Cairo residents reported limited or fee-based public internet access. Parents in Cairo frequently had to transport children to public Wi-Fi spots or rely on neighbors and relatives, adding logistical and emotional burdens to an already stressful period. Many parents described feelings of shame and helplessness over their inability to support their children's online learning, expressing guilt as their children fell behind due to technical limitations beyond their control.

"She looks at you and begs for internet to learn online, and you can't give it to her... it makes you wanna cry."

The children in Cairo were significantly more likely to miss school or homework due to internet issues or a lack of working devices. While Carbondale residents had newer and more numerous devices, Cairo more often relied on decade-old equipment or lacked devices entirely.

Despite similar intentions and efforts by teachers in both towns, structural disparities in access led to starkly different online education experiences during pandemic. Carbondale parents generally expressed satisfaction with how schools handled remote learning and praised the support their children received. In contrast, Cairo parents reported more emotional distress, academic decline, and persistent barriers to participation in online education. These findings highlight the interconnectedness of broadband infrastructure, affordability, community support, and public policy, and how their absence deepens the smart divide, particularly in persistently poor rural areas like small towns in Southern Illinois.

CHALLENGES IN TELEHEALTH ACCESS AND ADOPTION

Telehealth refers to healthcare services delivered through digital platforms, including video consultations, remote patient monitoring, and the sharing of medical data. This smart technology offers several benefits, including reduced travel time, improved access to care, and communication with providers, patient empowerment and greater support for managing chronic conditions. Telehealth is especially critical for rural communities where healthcare access is limited by provider shortages and geographic commuting barriers. It offers a practical solution for connecting patients to timely care without the need to travel long distances. However, despite its promise, our findings reveal that broad adoption of telehealth remains a challenge due to entrenched structural barriers, such as inadequate infrastructure, limited technical capabilities, and deep-rooted mistrust.

Patterns of Use and Perception

Carbondale residents generally had better internet infrastructure and were more likely to use various telehealth services and report more positive experiences overall compared to those in Cairo. Most telehealth users engaged in primary care follow-ups, with both convenience and cost savings cited as key motivators. For example, a mother of seven children said: “it’s not easy to pack all the [children] stuff and travel an hour or two to see the doctor and come back with multiple kids, so it is really helpful to do it online.” Another patient shared that “I could go anywhere, and I have great, actually have better care online because I was able to access somebody in Chicago who is a fantastic doctor versus with the limited options that are down here.” Non-Black residents in Carbondale showed higher telehealth adoption rates. Black respondents tend to use telehealth more for practical reasons like saving money on childcare and avoiding taking time off work. Privacy concerns remain the leading reason for not using telehealth across all communities and race, followed by limited digital skills and internet availability. Many patients expressed doubts about the security of virtual visits, and this concern was especially pronounced among Black residents in Cairo. For example, one person felt virtual appointments with a lack of safety and control, stating, “Don’t put me on the Internet like that. There’s nothing secure about being on the Internet. I don’t care how many firewalls.”

Infrastructure Deficits Undermine Access

Reliable internet connectivity and access to smart devices remain critical obstacles for adopting telehealth. In Carbondale, residents reported relatively better access to broadband and devices, while in Cairo, participants often lacked even basic internet at

home. While every patient interviewed in Carbondale had a device at home that they can use to access telehealth, several participants from Cairo did not. Carbondale residents had more choices for broadband providers, whereas Cairo had only one that was not even available to all residents. One patient shared that “I don’t have any internet access at home, since there is a tree that [they told me] blocks the internet, so I can’t get one.” Some respondents used outdated equipment or could only access care during work hours when stable internet and devices were available. A patient said that “I don’t have any laptop or device. The only device I use is thanks to my job. I use it when I’m there, but at home, I don’t have anything.” Another patient said that “I’ve done it from my job, my internet at home is breaking too much.” These examples reflect how infrastructure challenges limit access to telehealth.

“I would not trust my internet and I end up doing a phone call with my doctor. If I need a video call, I have to do it from my office.”

Healthcare Providers Perspectives

Healthcare providers interviewed in both towns shared compelling stories of how telehealth enabled life-saving interventions—from cardiac alerts via wearable tech to emergency consultations that wouldn’t have been possible otherwise. Despite recognizing its critical role, providers lamented that many patients, especially those in Cairo, lacked the digital tools or connectivity to use telehealth effectively.

Healthcare providers interviewed for this study expressed strong support for the potential of telehealth, particularly in improving timely access to care and reaching patients who might otherwise fall through the cracks. Several shared stories that underscored how virtual care can be lifesaving. One physician pointed out an urgent situation when “a patient’s pacemaker was going off, so he called me on the video call, and I saw that he was going on this weird rhythm and rushed him to the hospital. If he did not have access to telehealth, he would wait until Monday, and it would be too late.” Similarly, another physician described an instance when a patient shared health data from an Apple Watch during an online session, which allowed him to immediately detect a life-threatening condition: “A couple hours later he was on the operating table.” The providers were also lamented about the uneven uptake of telehealth and the barriers they observed in their patient populations. **Many reported that their patients lacked digital literacy, stable internet access, or the appropriate devices to fully participate in virtual visits. They also pointed to stark racial disparities in who used telehealth.** One physician shared: “I

“Trust, security and privacy is what a lot of my patients worry about.”

“All the horror TV stories about identity theft”.

can't remember the last time I had a Black patient online. My online patients are over 95% white, but it's not like that in-person." This difference underscores deeper issues of accessibility and trust. Several providers noted that trust and security, particularly among Black patients, often prevented adoption. Despite these concerns, most providers believed that telehealth should remain a part of their post-pandemic practice, especially for follow-ups, chronic care management, and therapy.

SMART DIVIDE - A COMPLEX INTERPLAY OF HUMAN, TECHNOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE

The expansion of contemporary digital technologies has transformed what it means to be “connected.” Access alone is no longer the only measure that matters. The smart divide goes beyond whether people have broadband internet or smartphone/tablet devices—it is about whether they can participate meaningfully in data-driven, digital services that shape their everyday lives. This project also explored how digital connectivity, human factors, and social infrastructure interact to shape smart inequality. We asked whether better broadband access helps reduce digital exclusion, how demographic characteristics influence participation, and what role social support systems may play in bridging these gaps.

Connectivity Alone Doesn't Close the Gap

Our findings challenge the common practice of relying solely on broadband expansion to address digital inequalities. Although improving connectivity is essential, it is not sufficient on its own. People require more than devices or Wi-Fi signals—they need the skills, confidence, motivation, and support necessary to effectively utilize digital tools in ways that enhance their lives. A robust network alone does little for someone unable to navigate an online portal, afford a data plan, or trust digital platforms. Without attending to these human and social dimensions of connectivity, infrastructure investments risk leaving the most vulnerable behind.

Speed, Performance, and Real-World Conditions Still Matter

While connectivity alone isn't sufficient to overcome digital inequalities, it remains a critical foundation—particularly in areas where even basic service is lacking or unreliable. Data-intensive activities such as telehealth and online learning require stable, high-speed internet, yet many rural communities continue to face slow speeds, dropped connections, and inconsistent coverage. Even when wireless service is technically available, its performance often falls short, especially in households with multiple users or in geographically challenging locations. Emerging solutions like 4G LTE, 5G, and satellite internet offer potential, but their effectiveness varies widely across diverse rural landscapes.

Human Factors Drive Smart Divide

Human factors—such as income, education, and digital literacy—are among the most powerful and consistent predictors of the smart divide. Lower-income households often struggle to afford reliable internet, replace outdated devices, or prioritize digital access

amid more immediate needs. Similarly, lower levels of education are closely linked to limited digital skills and reduced motivation to engage with online services. Even when infrastructure is available, these social and economic barriers continue to hinder meaningful participation in an increasingly smart and connected society.

The Role of Social Infrastructure

Social infrastructure –such as support from government programs, schools, libraries, community organizations, and friends and family support – plays a critical role in reducing the smart divide. Supportive relationships and robust community resources can help individuals navigate the digital ecosystem, build confidence, and access essential online services. Even in areas with poor connectivity, people with strong social networks are more likely to discover workarounds, obtain necessary assistance, and remain digitally engaged. Thus, social infrastructures serve as buffers against poor connectivity.

In rural areas specifically, institutions like libraries and schools often function as anchor points, addressing the "last mile" connectivity challenge by bringing internet access closer to those who need it most. These community organizations can extend internet availability, offer digital devices, and act as hubs for digital literacy training. However, many of these institutions currently face significant overburdened and underfunded, or risk being shut down entirely. Strengthening them is therefore essential—not only for improving digital access but also for enhancing the overall resilience of rural communities. However, there are still many open questions about what future social infrastructure should look like and how it can effectively support efforts to bridge the smart divide.

Yet, while social infrastructure undoubtedly helps individuals cope with digital connectivity challenges, our analysis indicates it may not fully compensate for the profound influence of human factors. This underscores the persistent and systemic nature of inequality. Longstanding disparities in income, education, and opportunity cannot be resolved through infrastructure improvements or community programs alone. Instead, addressing these disparities requires deeper structural changes, including sustained investment in education, workforce development, economic opportunities, and the cultivation of public trust. Without adopting this broader approach, digital inclusion efforts are likely to remain insufficient.

STRATEGIES FOR CLOSING THE DIVIDE

Technological Solutions

Wireless networks hold significant potential for bridging the rural smart divide, despite some limitations compared to wired broadband—most notably, lower average bandwidth. Still, the development of wireless infrastructure in rural areas depends heavily on supportive broadband policies and the advancement of next-generation technologies.

Emerging solutions like Starlink and 5G are expanding the possibilities for rural broadband access. Starlink, developed by SpaceX, employs a growing constellation of low-Earth orbit satellites to deliver high-speed internet nearly anywhere in the world. Because these satellites orbit closer to Earth than traditional ones, they provide faster speeds and lower latency. Starlink is already available in parts of the U.S., with coverage expanding rapidly. Current download speeds range from 50 Mbps to 250 Mbps. Once fully operational, Starlink is expected to offer global coverage and significantly reduce the infrastructure demands of rural broadband delivery—requiring only a satellite dish and a power source, with no need for buried cables or cell towers (McDowell 2020).

Meanwhile, 5G networks also offer opportunities to improve rural connectivity, supporting services such as remote learning and telehealth. Although traditional 5G deployments rely on dense networks of towers—less feasible in sparsely populated regions—using lower-frequency spectrum bands can extend coverage with fewer towers. This makes 5G a promising solution for delivering mobile broadband to underserved communities.

Planning Initiatives

The planning and development of “smart villages” offers a promising solution to the emerging smart divide. Conceptually, smart villages can be seen as the rural counterpart to smart cities, though the idea has received attention much later (Adamowicz and Zwolińska-Ligaj 2020). Zhang and Zhang (2020) define a smart village as a rural development strategy that leverages information and communication technology (ICT) to promote sustainable development, while also addressing the unique characteristics and needs of rural communities.

According to the European Union, smart villages emphasize local, community-led solutions—often (but not always) supported by digital technology—to make rural areas more attractive and to redefine their role in a rapidly digitizing economy (Hess et al. 2018). These initiatives are viewed as catalysts for innovating rural services and supporting smart rural development (Hess et al. 2018; Van Gevelt et al. 2018; Zavrtnik et al. 2018). Some examples of smart villages initiatives include: the 'Inner Areas

Strategy' in Italy in order to respond to rural depopulation, the 'Reciprocity Contracts' in France in order to build rural-urban linkages, the 'Smart Countryside' initiative in Finland to address depopulation and digital transition, and the 'Digital Villages' initiative in Germany to harness the digital transition (Hess et al. 2018). These efforts are gaining global traction (Holmes et al. 2015; Visvizi and Lytras 2018), yet they remain largely absent in rural America (Li et al. 2020), suggesting an untapped opportunity for U.S. rural development policy.

Policy Support

Compared to their urban counterparts, rural areas require greater support to overcome both the long-standing digital divide and the emerging smart divide. Smaller towns, which are often rural and typically consisting of 10,000 households or less, are especially vulnerable to these disparities (Broadband Models for Unserved and Underserved Communities 2020). Both established and innovative policy interventions are essential to closing this gap.

Federal and state support is vital to broadband infrastructure deployment in rural areas, where high capital costs and low population density lead to poor or nonexistent returns on investment. Prior to COVID19 pandemic, the Federal Communications Commission (FCC)'s Rural Digital Opportunity Fund (RDOF) primarily funded broadband service providers serving rural communities. During the pandemic, the *Coronavirus Aid, Relief, and Economic Security (CARES) Act* allocated billions of dollars to support distance learning, telehealth, and remote work, all of which require robust broadband infrastructure (Hovis et al. 2020). More recently, the *Infrastructure Investment and Jobs Act* remarkably expands federal investment into rural areas where households have historically lower access to broadband through federal programs administered by the U.S. Department of Commerce's National Telecommunications and Information Administration (NTIA), the FCC, and the U.S. Department of Agriculture (Congressional Research Services 2021). At the state level, almost every state has in-state programs for supporting broadband development. For example, the Illinois Office of Broadband administers the *Connect Illinois Broadband Infrastructure Grant Program*. Many states' broadband grant programs explicitly prioritize affordability, digital equity, and economic development, often using public-private partnerships as a delivery model (Sherman et al. 2021).

CONCLUSIONS

The smart divide is becoming one of the most pressing challenges for resilient, future-ready rural America. As the contrasting experiences of Carbondale and Cairo of Illinois show, the gaps between digitally connected and disconnected communities go far beyond whether households have broadband access or digital devices. It reflects the interaction of technology, human needs, and community support systems that together determine who can fully participate—and who is left out—in today’s increasingly smart and connected society.

The COVID-19 pandemic made these dynamics painfully pronounced. Carbondale students were able to shift to virtual learning with support from their school district and multiple internet options. In contrast, many families in Cairo relied on paper packets and spotty connections during the period. Racial disparities in telehealth adoption further revealed a critical barrier: lack of trust. As smart technologies meet long-standing inequalities, building trust through transparency and community involvement is essential for these technologies to succeed.

Looking ahead, infrastructure alone isn’t enough. Investments in broadband must go hand in hand with efforts to build digital skills, reduce social and economic barriers, and strengthen supporting organizations like libraries, schools, and local nonprofits that help people navigate the digital world. Recent federal place-based initiatives are a step in the right direction, connecting broadband expansion with workforce training, civic infrastructure, and user-friendly technical support. Success depends on sustained, locally tailored strategies that reflect the needs of individual communities.

The path forward requires comprehensive place-based strategies that address technological, human, and social dimensions simultaneously. Rather than expecting rural communities to replicate “smart city” models, we need to develop approaches that align with rural contexts and priorities by leveraging contemporary technologies and tools to strengthen existing community assets and relationships. The goal is not to adapt rural areas into an urban model, but to empower them to adopt technologies in ways that support their unique needs and aspirations—to develop future-ready and resilient rural communities on their own terms.

Finally, we must recognize that community institutions are not only critical service providers but valuable assets for rural development. When being properly funded and structured, they help residents stay connected, access essential services, and participate in the 21st Century digital economy. Without a more holistic and inclusive approach, efforts to close the smart divide will fall short, and many rural communities will continue to be left behind.

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